

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE REVENUE MANAGER IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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Abstract: Revenue management includes the use of analytics and performance data to assist those in the hotel industry foresee their customers' behavior. The data is then utilized to make appropriate decisions in regards to pricing and distribution strategies. The ultimate goal of revenue management is to have the right room for the right person at the right time and place. When this happens, you will be more likely to maximize your revenue, and in turn, your profit.

Key words: revenue manager, hospitality industry, demand of customer, business intelligence, pricing strategy.

Annotatsiya: Daromadni boshqarish bu mehmonxona sanoatida mijozlarning xatti-harakatlarini oldindan bilishda yordam beradigan tahlillar va ishlash ko'rsatkichlari ma'lumotlaridan foydalanishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu ma'lumotlar narx belgilash va taqsimot strategiyalari bo'yicha to'g'ri qarorlar qabul qilish uchun ishlatiladi. Daromadni boshqarishning asosiy maqsadi – kerakli joy va vaqtda kerakli mijoz uchun kerakli xonani taklif qilishdir. Shu orqali daromadingizni, shuningdek, foydangizni maksimal darajada oshirish ehtimoli yuqori bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: daromad menejeri, mehmonxona sanoati, mijozlar talabi, biznes razvedkasi, narx belgilash strategiyasi.

Аннотация: правление доходами включает использование аналитики и данных о производительности для того, чтобы помочь представителям гостиничной индустрии предвидеть поведение своих клиентов. Эти данные затем используются для принятия правильных решений в отношении стратегий ценообразования и распределения. Основная цель управления доходами – предоставить подходящий номер для нужного клиента в нужное время и месте. Это увеличивает вероятность максимизации дохода, а следовательно, и прибыли.

Ключевые слова: менеджер по доходам, гостиничная индустрия, спрос клиентов, бизнес-аналитика, стратегия ценообразования.

The hotel industry is one of the most important components of the wider service industry, catering to customers who require overnight accommodation. It is closely associated with the travel and hospitality industries, although there are notable differences in scope.

Revenue management is highly crucial to hoteliers because it allows them to maximize revenues and yields, using smart tech and big data. The main aim is to foresee market demand and react to changes in the market efficiently. Without a doubt, these are challenging times for the hospitality industry.

As you design your revenue management program, you may choose to compute fixed averages for some data and time periods and use rolling averages for others. For example, it may be helpful to know your average rooms sold for the first 14 days of last month and your average rooms sold for the past 14 days. If the most recent number is larger, you are likely experiencing an increase in room sales. Either way, the data you have collected and analyzed can help you better predict your future room sales.

Regardless of the type of averages they utilize, **RMs** must track their historical data because it is from sales histories that they will be better able to predict current and future operating data.

The information reached on how your customers think and perceive value will be ultimately utilized to match your supply to their demand. This will help you determine when it is best to hold onto a room until you can gain a higher price and how to recognize a drop in demand, signaling the time for discounted rates. The ultimate key to an effective revenue management strategy is having a way to make proper forecasts of your likely consumers' spending habits and the demand for your product. This can consist of past and current bookings, weather forecasts, tourism numbers, and other industry data. With this information, you will better be able to make informed adjustments when necessary.

The 4Ps of revenue management are: **Pricing, Positioning, Pace, and Performance**. We will cover each element individually as part of a 4-part blog series.

A hotel's revenue manager is responsible for setting prices that will maximize the hotel's profitability and meet its strategic goals. While this task might not sound daunting at first, it involves a mix of analytical skills, market research, critical thinking, and a little bit of gut instinct to make sound pricing decisions. Great revenue managers must also balance the hotel's mix of group and transient business, which entails negotiation between marketing and sales.

It involves promoting the most suitable accommodations to the appropriate client at the right prices and at the right times through the use of targeted distribution channels. This provides a cost-effective solution while still helping to ensure customer satisfaction.

This will often require the use of analytics and similar data points so that the most appropriate strategies can be developed. Here are some common factors that may be analyzed:

Predicting demand

Determining behaviors (such as the times of the year with the highest booking rates)

Understanding consumer spending habits

Developing dynamic pricing packages

Analysis of competition's pricing strategy thanks to business intelligence.

Understanding these concepts will allow management to make informed decisions while ensuring that any revenue generated can be used in the most efficient manner possible. In other words, **revenue management** depends upon addressing the “who, what, where, why, and how” of the hotel industry.

The **hospitality industry** is a vast and dynamic sector that encompasses a wide range of services primarily focused on accommodating guests and ensuring their satisfaction. This includes various segments such as hotels, resorts, restaurants, travel, event planning, and other tourism-related services. The industry's primary goal is to provide comfortable, enjoyable, and high-quality experiences for guests, while also ensuring financial sustainability and growth for businesses within it.

Importance of the Hospitality Industry

Economic Impact: The hospitality industry is a major contributor to global economies. It generates billions of dollars annually, providing millions of jobs worldwide. This includes jobs not only in hotels and restaurants but also in supporting industries such as construction, real estate, transportation, and manufacturing.

Employment Opportunities: The industry is one of the largest employers globally, offering a range of opportunities from entry-level positions in housekeeping to senior roles in hotel management. Moreover, hospitality careers can be quite diverse, encompassing customer service, event planning, culinary arts, travel and tourism, and more.

Cultural Exchange: Hospitality brings people from different parts of the world together, fostering cross-cultural understanding and appreciation. It plays a key role in tourism by providing travelers with opportunities to experience new destinations, local cuisine, and customs.

Technology Integration: As technology continues to evolve, the hospitality industry has embraced new innovations to improve guest experience and streamline operations. This includes the use of mobile apps for booking and check-in, artificial intelligence (AI) for personalization, and automation systems for better resource management.

In addition, to the state program on the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60, in accordance with it, the amount of tourist (hotel) fees transferred to the Tourism Support Fund from April 1, 2024 to April 1, 2026 for business entities providing hotel services will be allocated at the end of each quarter as subsidies.

In this case, when at least three rooms of the hotel are conveniently equipped by business entities for the use of wheelchairs, as well as displays and sound devices are installed for them to hear and see, these business entities will be charged the following subsidies for each specially equipped room in the following amounts:

For star hotels: 2 million soums;

For non-star hotels: 1 million soums.

Revenue management is not something to be taken lightly in achieving long-term success, as hoteliers handle historical and current data. It should also align with dynamic strategies, the needs of your hotel, and customers.

It goes without saying, of course, that **artificial intelligence** and automated processes play an important role in this sector. These systems have assisted in simplifying and automating all hotel operations, creating more memorable experiences as well as better profits for businesses.

Revenue management can also lead to greater innovation by providing data about services that the hotel could benefit from, which they may not have previously considered. Further reasons why **revenue management** is important: it can improve the efficiency of the hotel, drive down costs, improve demand forecasting, help decision-makers determine the right balance of staff, and give the hotel an edge over their competition.

Thus, **revenue management** is an essential component of hotel management and one that can help hotels become more profitable while providing their customers with the service and amenities they need. The **hospitality industry** plays a crucial role in the global economy, offering a broad range of services designed to enhance guest experiences while also driving profitability for businesses. From **revenue management**

to customer satisfaction, technology adoption, and sustainability, there are numerous facets to consider for success. The industry is constantly evolving, and professionals need to stay on top of trends, data analysis, and consumer behavior to remain competitive in a fast-paced market.

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